

О НЕКОТОРЫХ ЖАНРОВЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЯХ КОЛЫБЕЛЬНОЙ ПЕСНИ*Арутюнян А.Г.**Центр арменоведческих исследований Ширака НАН РА,
г. Гюмри Кандидат искусствоведения, доцент***ABOUT SOME GENRE FEATURES LULLABY SONG***Harutyunyan H.**Shirak Centre for Armenian Studies of NAS RA,
Gyumri PhD in Art, Associate Professor***АННОТАЦИЯ**

Колыбельная песня – один из уникальных фольклорных жанров. Он существует с древних времён и в каждом отдельном случае демонстрирует аутентичные черты творчества, присущие определённой народности. Статья посвящена музыковедческой характеристике жанра и обоснованию факта существования его поджанров на примере армянской музыки.

ABSTRACT

The lullaby is one of the unique folklore genres. refers to ohm, it has existed since ancient times and in each individual case demonstrates the authentic features of creativity inherent in a certain nationality. The article is devoted to the musicological characterization of the genre and the musicological substantiation of the existence of its subgenres.

Ключевые слова: колыбельная, песня, традиция, жанр, поджанр, стиль.

Keywords: lullaby, song, tradition, genre, subgenre, style.

The lullaby genre belongs to folklore, it has existed since ancient times and in each individual case demonstrates the authentic features of creativity inherent in a certain nationality. The simplified structure of the work, the calm tempo, the uncomplicated text - these features correspond to the main goal for which lullabies are created - to help the child fall asleep, to calm him down. Lullaby is one of the most natural and aesthetic forms of interaction between mother and baby, a simple but effective way to convey tender feelings to the baby, give him a sense of security and safety. [6]

The lullaby as a bedtime text has a rich content expression in the contexts of both children's folklore, children's literature and folklore. In the realm of children's folklore, the lullaby has a fairly distinct emphasis bedroom elements.

The specificity of the destination determines the musical features of the lullaby: the presence of short phrases, the predominance of consonant intervals. The rejection of dissonance in favor of euphony is necessary for a better perception of the work by ear. Most lullabies are played at a slow tempo and are often refrain-episode-refrain. The repetitive part is necessary to create the effect of soft hypnosis, lulling, and short couplets (often in one quatrain) contribute to the development of the plot.

“The nature, structure, semantic comprehensiveness, stylistic features and function of a lullaby as a text are determined by the listener, often by the state of mind of the lullaby. Therefore, it is very important to include the narrator in the process of studying the lullaby recipient factors. The receiver of the lullaby is always a listener is the child. In some cases, the text of

the cradle can be read by the researcher-researcher, in this situation the cradle changes its function.” [4]

A lullaby is usually a soothing song that is played to lull a baby to sleep. Lulling a child to sleep is a complex phenomenon, for the realization of which the child, the sleeper, the cradle, as well as speech, melody, and movement are necessary. Of course, this is only the operational side of the phenomenon, because in many cultures and in real depths it is more than just a phenomenon accompanying the baby to sleep. The lullaby can be considered one of the mandatory phenomena of human life, regardless of nationality, period, religious and other affiliation. A lullaby was sung to lull a child to sleep thousands of years ago, when there were not even the concepts of nation and nationality, and after the formation of this phenomenon, it became one of the guarantees of the preservation of the species, especially in the case of small nations or those in danger of assimilation. [1]

The lullaby is one of the oldest genres of folklore. Usually this is a melody or song sung by people to soothe and fall asleep. For the most part, the mechanisms of suggestion with the help of lulling songs have the setting on the work of the right hemisphere of the brain and affect emotions, the subconscious.

The oral text probably suggests a transitional process, it is recreated by becoming variant, which we cannot tell about author's lullabies. The process of re-creation is carried out by traditional lullabies, because they have the most emotional state of mind when singing a lullaby to a child, they gently present themselves to say, peppering the lullaby with new word units each time. Moreover, the traditional nursery rhymers want to tell more the child. [4]

Lullabies are one of the most vibrant types of Armenian folk songs. Their first samples are found in the Middle Ages, and already in the 18th-19th centuries, are written down by collectors and find a place in the literature dedicated to Armenian folk culture. Lullabies are the result of centuries-old creativity of Armenian mothers. Daily work and life, festive life and beliefs are

reflected in them. Along with all that, lullabies reveal the Armenian worldview and have an important educational value.

To give emotionality and expressiveness to the text and all that to the child listener to convey, the native lullaby chooses derogatory, diminutive, and sometimes exaggerated word units.

4 Նա նիկ բա լա ջան, նա նիկ, նա նիկ դար դար է նիմ դար դար, դար դար,
 դար, ա նուշ բա լա ջան նա նիկ է նեմ ու բըն ցը նեմ իմ ա նուշ-բա լին
 7
 8 նա նիկ բա լես նա նիկ, նա նիկ հա սանք հայ
 9 ռե նիք, հայ ռե նիքն ա նուշ է ես չեմ հե ռա
 10 նա, կաթ նա տուր մայ ղիկ ջան քեզ չեմ մո ռա նա, նա նիկ բա
 լա ջան, նա նիկ, նա նիկ է նեմ ու բըն ցը նեմ իմ ա նուշ բա լին:

Armenian folklore as a traditionally preserved and transmitted phenomenon stands out for its diversity. This is first of all expressed by the presence of different branches in folk art, which, of course, having commonalities, at the same time are quite different in their poetic, melodic thinking and structure. Beginning in different periods and conditions, national thinking has been manifested in each of them to a greater or lesser extent.

In Armenian traditional life, through cradles, the mother expressed her love for her child, sent her admonition and blessing-prayer to him, sought the intercession of the saints for her child's health, peaceful and

prosperous life. The songs feature the Holy Mother of God, from whom the mother expected daily intercession for her child, Saint Sargis, who was supposed to protect her son from dangers, Saint Gregory the Illuminator, whose graces the mother wanted to see the child endowed with. The Church and the Holy Cross are also remembered. According to folk beliefs, every child has its own guardian angel, who, with outstretched wings, stands over the child's ear, protecting it from evil forces. For the same purpose, the mother decorated the crib with crosses.

0-րոր, օ-րոր, օ-րոր, օ-րոր, օ-րոր է-նեմ, օ րոր, օ-րոր, է-նեմ, օ-
 4
 րոր է-նեմ օ-րոր րո - ցին, քուն կը-տա-նի ա - նուշ քա - լին, նա-նիկ
 8
 է-նե ա-նուշ քա-լես, քը-նի, քը-նի, շուտ մե-ծա-նաս, մե-զի պի - տա-նի մարդ
 12
 դառ-նաս, օ - րոր է - նեմ, օ - րո - րո-ցին իմ ա-նուշ
 15
 քա-լին, նա-նիկ, նա-նիկ նա - նիկ:

Komitas women attaches great importance to performances. he believes that the guardians of family morals and customs are women, that through them the national spirit passes from generation to generation.

The spiritual bond between mother and child was created and strengthened through a lullaby. A lullaby was the beginning of a child's artistic perceptions, which would later shape his mental formation. With the lullaby he heard from his mother, the child became a communicator of his familiar Armenian song. Even today, lullabies have not lost their importance, so we consider it necessary to help young mothers bring back our

wonderful lullabies, which, apart from their practical function, also have a high artistic value.

The dominant motifs in lullabies (praise to the child, good wishes, etc.) were often combined with motifs reflecting the personal life of the singing mother. Expressing different aspects and realities of the socio-historical life of the people, family-domestic relations, various beliefs and ideas, lullabies have historical cognitive value. The most developed samples of Armenian folk songs are fully formed songs in their poetic-musical form and content and constitute a significant genre of national traditional lyrical singing.

Բա - լես քը - նի օ - րոր օ - րոր իմ քա - լին,
 Ա-նուշ քը-նով քը-նի քա - լես շուտ մե - ծա - նա իմ քա - լես:
 Մե-ծա - նաս շուտ քո օ - րե - րովդ հաս-նես պա - պա-յիդ թև - ին
 Պա-պադ, կը-գա քեզ բեր - նե - րով օ - րոր օ - րոր իմ քա - լին:

“Today, many scientists and researchers are inclined to the idea that in any corner of the world, regardless of education, religion, race, a mother sitting in front of a child's crib has similar feelings and attitudes, and her song carries the same charge and self-forgetting love for the baby, regardless of geographical location. : In those songs, the content, thematics, and nature are largely the same”. [1]

Komitas valued the lullabys as the authority of women, associating with them the task of preserving

and transmitting national folk music. However, recorded naniks from male performances are also interesting examples and valuable material for observation. In one case, it is a reproduction of an elaborate song recorded by memory, in another case, a fictional form in the genre of rocking in one's own musical thinking. Lullaby is one of the most nationally characteristic and most complex works of Armenian folk song. [3]

Նա նա նա իմ բա - լա

փոք թես դու շուտ մե - ծա - նաս

նա նի նա նի նա - նի ջան:

Here, more than in any other song, the changes occurring within the genre, lines of gradual development, genre penetrations are prominent.

A lullaby is usually a soothing song that is played to lull a baby to sleep. Lulling a child to sleep is a complex phenomenon, for the realization of which the child, the sleeper, the cradle, as well as speech, melody, and movement are necessary. Of course, this is only the operational side of the phenomenon, because in many cultures and in real depths it is more than just a phenomenon accompanying the baby to sleep. The lullaby can be considered one of the mandatory phenomena of human life, regardless of nationality, period, religious and other affiliation. A lullaby was sung to lull a child to sleep thousands of years ago, when there were not even the concepts of nation and nationality, and after the formation of this phenomenon, it became one of the guarantees of the preservation of the species, especially in the case of small nations or those in danger of assimilation.

The traditional setting provided a natural course of generational change, where a lullaby sung for one person became one sung by himself for the next generation. And the oral art created especially in rural areas was typical, because once upon a time people there lived in a closed and unmixed environment with traditional creativity.

The close relationships and pleas of different song types in lullabies are primarily connected with the expansion of the boundaries of thematic content.

“The lullaby is one of the oldest and at the same time one of the most vibrant genres of the Armenian folklore song heritage. It can be argued that throughout the ancient Armenian history, lullaby has always been the most important expression of the emotional world and sensibility of the Armenian woman. In Armenian folklore, and especially in the genre system of lyrical folklore, the interest in this genre does not decrease. The reason is both the variety of genre characteristics and the abundance of means of expression. The vital interrelationship and artistic depth of the inventor's sudden fictional abilities and their equivalent means of expression are especially important. It is because of these characteristics that the lullaby has retained its vitality in Shirak's modern musical folklore as well. In its rich musical heritage, where the most important musical-historical characteristics of Western Armenia, especially High Hayk, are concentrated, lullabies are still remembered and invented anew, preserving the fundamental principles of composition of Armenian monodic songwriting in the best possible way.” [2]

4 Նա-նիկ ա-սեմ բա - լիս, նա - նար բա-լա ջան նա-նար, նա-նար,
 7 խորն է բը-նե բա-լի-կըս, բա-լա ջան նա-նա նա - նիկ բա-լա
 11 ջան, նա-նիկ, նա - նիկ, տա-րեք ինձ իմ հայ-րե-նիք,
 14 հայ-րե - նի - քից հե-ռա - ցել եմ, բա-լա ջան, նա-նիկ, նա -
 17 նիկ, խեղճ պան - դուխտ եմ, տուն չու-նիմ, բա-լից բա - ժան - վել
 եմ, տը-խուր, տը-խուր, քուն չու-նեմ, բա-լա ջան:

Each storyteller is distinguished by his storytelling style, with something to say. Linguistic reality (lullaby texts) accordingly expresses the imaginary, which is always external out of the daily rhythm and approaches the day-to-day feeling towards the child to an exceptional manifestation of feeling.

“Having analysed the sources of folklore, we can firmly state that the Armenian culture has abundant childlore and themes on children’s folklore. Naturally it is impossible to present the bulk of the background materials in a comprehensive way, but our study shows that children’s folklore as a unique type of folklore is stable, fixed and (like an oak) stands aside the adult folklore. This is supposing one of the reasons why children’s folklore materials are mainly included in collective works of Ethnography and Folklore Volumes, books. Children’s folklore or Childlore should be viewed as a complete unit of folklore”. [5]

CONCLUSION: The lullaby has become one of the genres that stand out for its national, traditional, typical musicality and express that typicality genre. Traditional, stabilized cradles passed down from generation to generation, in particular, reflect the culture from which they originate. Being a universal phenomenon, having many commonalities, the cradle of each nation is a symbol of the cultural identity of the given people.

References

1. Hakobyan A. Armenian traditional Lullabies. A dissertation submitted in partial satisfaction of the requirements of the degree Doctor of Arts. Yerevan, 2022. (in Armenian).
2. Harutyunyan H. The Lullaby Genre in Shirak's Contemporary Musical Folklore // “Historical and Cultural Heritage of Shirak: Contemporary Issues of Armenology” Dedicated to the 25th Anniversary of Shirak Center for Armenological Studies of NAS RA, Gyumri-Yerevan, 2022, pp. 232-235.
3. Janikyan H. Antiquities of Akn. Tiflis. Printing of M.D. Rotinyants. 1895. 516 p.. (In Armenian).
4. Matikyan H. The personage of lullaby singer in England and Armenian folk lullaby texts. «Scientifik works» of SCAS NAS RA. Gyumri. 2015. V. XVIII, pp. 204-209. (in Armenian).
5. McDowall R., Matikyan H. Childlore and childrens folklore in the UK in Armenia (Historical and Current Perspective). «Scientifik works» of SCAS NAS RA, Gyumri. 2021. V.1, pp. 218-228.
6. Trainer L.J, Trehub S.E., Singing to infants: Lullabies and play songs, in: Rovee-Collier, C., Lipsitt, L. P. & Hayne H. (Eds.), Advances in infancy research. Stanford, 1998, pp. 43-77.